

Machine-learning abstractions for component-based self-optimizing systems

Michal Töpfer, Milad Abdullah, Tomáš Bureš, Petr Hnětynka and Martin Kruliš

Charles University, Czech Republic.

Contributing authors: topfer@d3s.mff.cuni.cz; abdullah@d3s.mff.cuni.cz;
buress@d3s.mff.cuni.cz; hnetynka@d3s.mff.cuni.cz; krulis@d3s.mff.cuni.cz;

Abstract

This paper features an approach that combines machine learning abstractions with a component model. We target modern self-optimizing systems; thus, we integrate the machine learning abstractions into our ensemble-based component model DEECo. We further endow the DEECo component model with abstractions for specifying self-optimization heuristics, which address coordination among multiple components. We demonstrate these abstractions in the context of an Industry 4.0 use case. We argue that incorporating machine learning and optimization heuristics is the key feature for modern smart systems, which are to learn over time and optimize their behavior at runtime to deal with uncertainty in their environment.

Keywords: Self-adaptation, ensembles, machine-learning, heuristics

1 Introduction

Modern smart systems (such as smart manufacturing in Industry 4.0, smart traffic, smart buildings, i.e., systems composed of multiple software and hardware components that closely interact with the real world) increasingly aim at providing highly optimized behavior that copes with the high uncertainty and variability of their surrounding environment. This classifies them as representatives of *self-adaptive systems*, which are systems that monitor their performance and their ability to meet their goals and adapt their behavior to cope with changes in themselves and in their environment.

Modern smart systems are often composed of multiple components, which are required to coordinate their operation. This means that the system adaptation and optimization have to be done in a coordinated manner too.

Traditionally these systems have been designed by providing a set of adaptation rules that were supposed to identify principal states and changes in the environment and reconfigure the system. However, with more and more emphasis on data and with the increasing amounts of data the modern systems collect and are able to exploit in their operation, the specification using a fixed set of adaptation rules becomes increasingly more complex and hard to do (mainly due to the fact that the model behind the data is unknown and potentially changing).

A recent trend in modern smart systems is to use machine learning, especially neural networks, to help the system make adaptation and optimization decisions. However, machine learning is still used in a rather ad-hoc manner without having been systematically embedded in the architecture of the systems.

The main problem is that there is a lack of architectural models for the specification of system components that would provide abstractions for machine learning and other kinds of optimizations based on data observed by the system. As a result, every smart system that employs machine learning or some kind of optimization has to create its own architectural abstractions. This not only means duplicating the work but also requiring an expert in machine learning to be able to implement the abstractions correctly.

Based on our experience, we see that machine learning is typically needed for classification and regression, thus allowing predicting the current or future state of the system. However, in addition to this, when dynamic systems are considered, a very pertinent question that demands machine learning is at which point in time the system will change its state.

With self-organizing systems, we can also perceive that they have to address problems that are of a more combinatorial nature—e.g., how to pair up components to best respond to a situation at hand. These problems are often difficult to solve with supervised ML methods. However, often the right solution can be approximated by unsupervised learning methods (e.g., k-means) or various heuristics. However, the problem of lacking abstractions, even for these problems, is still present.

In this paper, we address this problem of lacking architectural abstractions by providing a novel component model (called ML-DEECo) that features dedicated abstractions—*estimates*—for machine learning (currently only supervised learning) and optimization heuristics (used mainly for coordination problems).

The ML-DEECo model is an extension of our previous DEECo component model [1]. Similar to DEECo, it is based on the concept of autonomic component ensembles, which are situation-based coordination groups of components that cooperate (within a given situation) to achieve a common goal.

In this paper, we demonstrate the main concepts of ML-DEECo on a use-case that stems from our previous project with industry. The use-case is about access control in a factory in Industry 4.0 settings.

We support the concepts of ML-DEECo by an implementation in Python, which can process the

ML-DEECo abstractions and use them to automatically realize the complete learning loop (consisting of data collection, model training, and inference at runtime). By this, we show the usefulness of ML-DEECo as it saves not only the time needed to develop the learning loop but also the expertise needed to do that. The implementation is part of the replication package that comes along with the paper [2].

Extending upon [3], we present in this paper a detailed description of introducing machine learning concepts in the ML-DEECo component model together with an extended evaluation of our approach. In particular, we added a detailed description of all introduced kinds of estimates and details about training the estimates (i.e., their semantics), and we extended the evaluation via another implemented simulation. Also, we updated a discussion about the limitations of the approach.

The structure of the text is as follows. Section 2 describes the running example and, based on the example, introduces ensemble-based component systems. Section 3 presents the machine-learning concepts of ML-DEECo while Section 4 discusses the application of heuristics. Section 5 evaluates the presented approach, and Section 6 compares it with related work. Section 7 concludes the paper.

2 Running example and background

In this paper, we build on the running example from recent work on dynamic security rules by Al-Ali et al. [4]. The example is a simplified version of a real-life scenario concerning access to a smart factory and it is taken from our recent project with industrial partners. The example is visualized in Figure 1.

The factory consists of several working places, each with an assigned shift of workers. The workers come to the factory in the morning. They have to go through the main gate to enter the factory. Then, they have to grab a protective headgear at a headgear dispenser inside the factory and they can continue to their workplace. The workers are not allowed to enter the workplaces of the other shifts in the factory.

To ensure security and safety in the factory, several rules are defined. For example, the workers are

Fig. 1 Factory example

allowed to enter the factory at the earliest 30 minutes before their shift starts. The rule is enforced by a smart lock at the main gate. Another rule defines that the worker can only enter his work place if they are wearing the protective headgear. We can see that the security rules are dynamic as their effect depends on time (we allow workers to the factory at most 30 minutes before their shift) and on of workers (whether they wear the headgear or not).

The scenario further deals with replacing the workers who are late for their shift with standbys. For each shift in the factory, we have a defined set of standby workers. If a worker does not arrive at the factory sufficiently (16 minutes) before their shift starts, they are canceled for the day and a standby is called to replace them. As the actual time of arrival of the workers to the factory varies, it brings uncertainty to the system, which is an opportunity to use a machine-learning-based estimate to deal with it. Furthermore, the assignment of the standbys can be a hard optimization problem if the sets of standbys for the shifts overlap, so it can be dealt with using a heuristic approach.

2.1 Modeling dynamic security rules with components and ensembles

We build our approach on the concept of autonomic component *ensembles*; in particular, we are using the abstractions of the DEECo ensemble-based component model [5]. In this section, we describe the concepts of ensembles that are necessary for understanding the paper.

Components represent the entities in our system (factory, rooms, dispenser, workers) and they are described by the *component type*. There are multiple instances (simply referred to as “components” in the paper) of each of the component types (i.e., multiple workers, rooms, etc.). Each of the components has a state represented as a set of data fields. Components that we cannot control directly (workers in our case) are referred to as “beyond control components”. The state of these components is only observed or inferred.

Ensembles represent dynamically formed groups of components that correspond to a coordinated activity. As for the components, the ensembles are described by their *ensemble type*, which can be instantiated multiple times. A single component can be selected in multiple ensemble instances at the same time—we call this that the component is a “member” of the respective ensemble instance. The ensemble prescribes possible data interchange among the components in the ensemble and also the group-wise behavior (e.g., a coordinated movement).

Technically, an ensemble type specifies the (1) roles, (2) situation, and (3) actions.

The *roles* determine which components are to be included in the ensemble (i.e., components that should be members of the ensemble). Roles are either static or dynamic. The static ones are specified when the ensemble is instantiated and cannot change. They provide the identity to the ensemble instance (e.g., a shift for which the ensemble is instantiated). There cannot exist two ensemble

instances of the same type that are equal in the assignment of their static roles.

The static roles are specified as a tuple: (i) type of component instances in the role, (ii) cardinality of the role.

The cardinality of the role is simply an interval determining the minimum and maximum number of component instances referred to by the role.

On the other hand, the dynamic roles are populated dynamically based on the situation in the system. The dynamic roles are specified as a triple: (i) type of component instances in the role, (ii) cardinality of the role, and (iii) condition over components in the role.

While the type and cardinality are the same as in the case of static roles, the condition further determines if a component may be selected for the role. The condition is parameterized by the component being selected for the dynamic roles and by the static roles (i.e. attributes of components in the static roles).

The situation is a condition over static roles that determines whether the ensemble should be instantiated.

The actions are activities to be executed when the ensemble is instantiated. They differ based on the target domain and have no influence on how ensembles are instantiated. In the case of our running example, we use two actions: *allow* and *notify*. The *allow* action assign some permission to a component. The *notify* action send a notification to a component (e.g. to let a standby worker know that they have been assigned to a shift).

Ensembles can be hierarchically nested, i.e., an ensemble can be defined as an inner one within another ensemble. This allows for the decomposition of complex conditions into simpler ones and thus makes the whole specification more easily manageable. Instances of an inner ensemble can be created only if there is an instance of the outer ensemble.

The ensembles are instantiated and dissolved dynamically and continuously as the state of the system changes. This instantiation of the ensembles and their dissolution is performed automatically by the ML-DEECo runtime framework.

An ensemble is instantiated for each possible assignment of static roles such that the situation condition is true and there exist components that can be assigned to the dynamic roles to satisfy the cardinality bounds and the dynamic role condition.

The instantiation is attempted periodically. In case of our running example, since this is run as a simulation, we perform the instantiation (and dissolution) of ensembles in every simulation step.

For our example, ensembles are used to express the security rules in the system. They dynamically grant/revoke access permissions to individual components.

Listing 1 shows a part of the specification of the running example. It represents the components and ensembles as illustrated in Figure 2. There are 6 types of components: Door, Dispenser (of protective headgear), Factory, WorkPlace, Shift and Worker. Each of them is described by a set of their fields.

```

1 component type Door:
2   field position: Position
3
4 component type Dispenser:
5   field position: Position
6
7 component type WorkPlace
8   field position: Position
9
10 component type Factory
11   field entryDoor: Door
12   field dispenser: Dispenser
13   field workplaces[*]: Workplace
14
15 component type Worker
16   field position: Position
17   field hasHeadgear: boolean
18
19 component Shift
20   field workPlace: Workplace
21   field startTime: Time
22   field endTime: Time
23   field assigned[*]: Worker # an original list of
    assigned workers
24   field workers[*]: Worker # a list of actually
    working workers
25   field standBys[*]: Worker
26
27 ensemble type AccessToFactory
28   static role shift: Shift
29   situation shift.startTime - 30 <= now <=
    shift.endTime + 30
30   dynamic role workers[*]: Worker
31     each worker in workers:
32       (worker in shift.assigned and not
        worker.canceled)
33       or worker in shift.calledStandbys
34   action allow workers enter factory
35
36 ensemble type CancelLateWorkers
37   static role shift: Shift
38   situation shift.startTime - 16 <= now <=
    shift.endTime
39   dynamic role lateWorkers[*]: Worker

```


Fig. 2 Factory example with visualized ensembles

```

40  each worker in lateWorkers:
41    worker in shift.assigned and not
      worker.isAtFactory
42  action notify lateWorkers with canceled
43  inner ensemble type ReplaceLateWithStandbys
44  dynamic role standBys[lateWorkers.size]: Worker
45    each worker in standBys:
46      worker in shift.standBys
47  action notify standBys with calledIn

```

Listing 1 An excerpt of the example specification

Further, ensemble types are specified. Due to the paper space limits, we show here only a few of them. In Figure 2, sample instances of ensembles are represented as the hand-drawn oval shapes.

The `AccessToFactory` assigns to the workers the access-to-factory permission. The static role `shift` (line 28) determines the identity of the ensemble instance, i.e., the ensemble is instantiated for a selected shift and there is only one ensemble instance of `AccessToFactory` for a particular shift.

The `situation` (line 29) is a predicate determining under which conditions the ensemble has to be instantiated. In this particular case, the ensemble is instantiated from 30 minutes before the shift starts till 30 minutes after the shift ends.

The dynamic role `workers` (line 30) selects all the workers which are assigned to the shift. These are workers that have been assigned to the shift and that have not been canceled due to being late, plus the standbys called to fill in for the late workers. This is stated on lines 32–33. The

definition of the role specifies the cardinality, the type of components assigned to the role, and the condition that has to hold for each component in the role.

The workers selected in the dynamic role are assigned with permission to enter the factory (line 34).

Similar to the `AccessToFactory`, our specification contains ensembles `AccessToDispenser` and `AccessToWorkplace`, which differ only in what they regulate the access to. Since they are very similar, we omitted them in the paper.

The next ensemble—`CancelLateWorker` (line 36) serves for canceling workers that are late. The static role pins the ensemble instance to a shift. The dynamic role selects workers that are late (i.e., they are not in the factory 16 minutes before the shift start). Those workers are then canceled from the shift (line 42). This is done by notifying them and the system about being canceled.

To replace the canceled workers, there is a subensemble (`ReplaceLateWithStandbys` in line 43) of the `CancelLateWorker` ensemble. It selects the necessary number of standbys to fill in for the canceled workers. The cardinality of the `standBys` role is equal to the number of canceled workers. The standbys are notified by the ensemble about being called in (line 47).

All the described ensembles are illustrated in Figure 2. The figure also shows other two ensembles

(omitted from the listing due to the space constraints but defined in the complete example in the replication package). They are `AccessToWorkspace` assigning permissions to access the particular workplace and `AccessToDispenser` assigning permission to obtain the headgear.

3 Estimates

In this section, we present the extension of the DEECo component model, which brings in machine-learning-based estimates. We call the extended component model ML-DEECo. Though we demonstrate the concepts on the running example, our approach is general and can be used in other use cases as well. The ML-DEECo framework allows the architect of the system to include the estimates inside both components and ensembles and to use the estimated values for adaptation decisions. The Python implementation, together with a more detailed description of all the provided abstractions, is available in the replication package [2].

3.1 Estimates definition

In our recent projects, we have identified several use cases, where machine learning would be beneficial to a proactive self-adaptation of the system. Several of these use cases exhibited the same patterns—we needed to predict a future state of a component and/or ensemble. The machine learning algorithms can easily be used in such situations as the future state will be known at some point in time in the future so we can formulate the problem as supervised machine learning and use the observed value for the training of the machine-learning-based estimate.

The supervised machine learning models use an observation of the current state of the component or ensemble (these are the *inputs* of the model) to predict the future state of the component or ensemble. Later, when the true future state of the component or ensemble can be observed (*true outputs* or *targets*), we can use the true observed value for the training (improvement of the predictions) of the machine learning model.

Based on our previous experience with designing ensemble-based systems and analysis, we have identified the following three kinds of estimates

based on where they can be applied in an architecture, i.e., on (i) a component, (ii) an ensemble, and (iii) a component-ensemble pair. Further, we can divide component-attached estimates into two sub-categories based on the semantics. The estimate can either be attached to (i) a component type (the prediction is the same for all instances of the particular component type) or to (ii) a component instance (each instance has its own predictions). Figure 3 summarizes the kinds of estimates.

Fig. 3 Kinds of estimates

In the rest of this subsection, we describe all the estimate kinds in detail.

3.1.1 Component instance applied estimate

In the first case, the estimate serves as a special synthesized field of the component instance and is parameterized by values of other component fields (that are not estimates). For example, the `Worker` component can have an estimate predicting whether the particular worker would be willing to be activated as a “standby” (in the case the selection as a called-in standby is voluntary). The estimate could be parameterized by the current day-of-week and would be trained on the history of the particular worker’s willingness to be activated as the standby.

To construct the estimate, there can be either a separate machine-learning model for each worker or a common machine-learning model parameterized by the particular worker. The latter option is usually preferred as it allows for generalization among the workers (we can assume that the behavior of all workers is more or less similar).

Listing 2 shows a specification of a worker component with an estimated “willingness to be a standby” (the specification extends the `Worker` specification from Listing 1). Line 3 defines the synthesized field with the estimate. The estimate is parameterized by two inputs: the day of the week (line 4) and an identification of the particular

worker (line 5). The guard on line 6 is used to indicate when to collect the data for training of the model—we are only interested in using the estimate when the worker is being notified by the `calledIn` notification (as for example on line 47 in Listing 1). The output is specified on line 7 reading the value indicating whether the worker accepted the call in notification or not. Assuming that the worker must accept the notification within 15 minutes after the notification, the value is read precisely at that time, which is denoted by `@ T+15`.

```

1 component type Worker
2 ... # regular fields
3 value estimate standbyWillingness:
4 input dayOfWeek
5 input id
6 input-guard worker notified with calledIn
7 output worker.acceptedCallIn @ T+15

```

Listing 2 An example of the component-instance applied estimate

3.1.2 Component type applied estimate

An example of an estimate for all instances of a single component type can be as follows. Assume there are production *machines* in the factory that produce parts. The produced parts are monitored for defects, and a failure rate is periodically evaluated for each individual machine. If the failure rate exceeds a certain threshold, the machine has to be turned off, and maintenance is called to repair the machine.

A useful quantity that can be estimated for such machines is how long the failure rate will stay below the given threshold, i.e., how long the machine will keep running without maintenance. The current failure rate and time since the last repair can be used to parameterize the estimate (assuming the failure rate close to the threshold indicates that the machine will have to be turned off soon). If the estimate predicts that the machine will fail soon, maintenance can be called to check the machine in advance, i.e., before it actually fails. This can save the time needed for the maintenance to arrive as the machine will keep producing parts during that time (contrary to the scenario where maintenance is called after the machine fails).

The difference from the previous example is that the estimate does not depend on the particular machine instance (the machine id is not among the inputs). We only use the current state of the machine and have a common prediction model for

all instances of the `ProductionMachine` component type.

Another difference to the previous example is that in this case, a future value of a field (i.e., the future state of the component) is not predicted but rather the time until a certain event happens in the system. The event is specified using a condition over the component state—the predicted event is then given by the condition becoming true. We call the kind of prediction *time-to-condition* estimate.

A particular specification of the machine is given in Listing 3. Line 5 defines the synthesized field with the estimate. The `time-to-condition` denotes the kind of the estimate (time until a condition becomes true). The condition (line 8) corresponds to the event of failure of the machine, i.e., that the machine `failureRate` exceeds the given threshold. The estimate is parameterized by the current failure rate of the machine (line 6). The guard (line 7) indicates that we want to collect training data for the estimate only when the machine is running. The estimated value is used on line 10 (if the machine fails soon, maintenance is called).

```

1 component type ProductionMachine
2 field isRunning: bool
3 field failureRate: float
4 field timeSinceLastRepair: int
5 time-to-condition estimate timeToFailure:
6 input failureRate
7 input-guard isRunning
8 condition failureRate > threshold
9 # use of the estimate
10 if timeToFailure() < ... then:
11 callMaintenance()

```

Listing 3 An example of the component-type applied estimate

3.1.3 Ensemble applied estimate

In this case, i.e., applying an estimate on an ensemble, an estimate is defined as a particular ensemble property and then can be used in the ensemble conditions (in the situation and/or the dynamic role selectors). The estimate is parameterized by values obtained from global variables and static roles of the ensemble. For example, if the running example is extended by the automated planning of shifts (i.e., allocating workers to shifts), there can be an ensemble with the estimate predicting the best number of workers in order to reach expected productivity goals. This prediction would be based

on the day-of-week and start time of the shift (morning, afternoon, evening).

The example specification is in Listing 4. The `ShiftWorkersAssignment` ensemble serves for selecting workers for each shift (which is assigned to the ensemble as a static role on line 2). The `situation` (line 4) specifies when the ensemble should be instantiated—in this case, 24 hours (24·60 minutes) before the start of the shift. The `necessaryWorkers` estimate (line 5) provides estimates of the number of necessary workers for the shift. The `dayOfWeek` and `startTime` of the shift are used as inputs of the estimate (lines 6 and 7).

The most complicated part of the example is the specification of the true outputs (line 8). Here we assume that the true output value can be computed when the shift ends—the `T + 60 * 24 + shift.duration` on line 9 is precisely the time of the end of the shift as the ensemble was instantiated at time `shift.startTime - 60 * 24` (as specified in the situation—line 4), so if we replace the `T` by the time of initiation, we get `shift.startTime - 60 * 24 + 60 * 24 + shift.duration`, which is equal to `shift.startTime + shift.duration`. To compute the true output, we assume the existence of a function `computeNecessaryWorkers`. If we assume a linear dependence of the productivity on the number of workers, the `computeNecessaryWorkers` function can be realized as `workers.count * expectedProductivity / productivity`. We can then use the estimated necessary number of workers in the cardinality condition of the workers dynamic role (line 11). Other conditions for the selection of workers are not discussed in this example.

```

1 ensemble type ShiftWorkersAssignment
2   static role shift: Shift
3   # assign workers 24 hours before the shift
4   situation shift.startTime - 60 * 24 == now
5   value estimate necessaryWorkers:
6     input dayOfWeek
7     input shift.startTime
8     output computeNecessaryWorkers()
9     @ T + 60 * 24 + shift.duration
10  dynamic role workers[*]: Worker
11  cardinality necessaryWorkers
12  ... # other conditions for selecting the workers
    for the shift
13  action notify workers with shiftAssigned

```

Listing 4 An example of the ensemble applied estimate

3.1.4 Component-Ensemble pair applied estimate

The last option—applying an estimate to the component-ensemble pair—is the most complex one. In this case, we associate the estimate with a component that has been dynamically selected in an ensemble.

As an example, we use machine learning for the adaptation of the replacement of late workers. A traditional rigid solution is to set a threshold for when the workers have to be inside the factory. In our case, the baseline approach is to cancel the workers if they are not present in the factory 16 minutes before the start of their shift. This, however, does not deal well with the uncertainty of the arrival of the workers. To replace the rigid approach, we suggest using a machine-learning-based estimate to predict whether a worker will come on time or not. This can be expressed as an estimate assigned to a dynamic role of an ensemble type as shown in Listing 5.

```

1 ensemble type CancelLateWorkers
2   static role shift: Shift
3   situation shift.startTime - 30 <= now <=
    shift.endTime + 30
4   dynamic role lateWorkers[*]: Worker
5   with value estimate willArrive:
6     output worker.isAtFactory @ T+<1,30>
7     input dayOfWeek
8     guard worker.shift == shift
9     each worker in lateWorkers
10    not worker.isAtFactory and not (willArrive @
    shift.startTime)
11  action notify lateWorkers with cancelled

```

Listing 5 Machine-learning-enabled ensemble specification – Cancel late workers.

The dynamic role for finding late workers is specified on line 4. We assign an estimate to this role on line 5 to predict whether the worker will come to the factory or not. We use the prediction to determine whether we should cancel the worker or not. That is done on line 10 in the membership condition of the role – we use the estimate to predict whether the worker will be at the factory at the time the shift starts.

To be able to use the estimate, we need to specify its inputs and outputs. The output of the estimate is the future value of the `worker.isAtFactory` attribute (line 6). By `T+<1,30>`, we indicate that we want to construct a model which is able to predict this value in a range of 1 to 30 minutes into the future. The input of the model is the day

of the week on which the shift takes place (line 7). Furthermore, we define a guard on line 8, which indicates the validity of the training data – here, as we have an instance of the ensemble for each shift, we only want to collect data about the workers from the one shift and not the other shifts.

3.2 Training of the estimates

The specification of estimates in the component/ensemble definitions is enough to be able to collect data automatically and train the machine learning model, which is done by the ML-DEECo framework runtime. The semantics of the estimates is as follows.

3.2.1 Value estimate

The estimate predicts an attribute from the future state of the system. In our example, the `willArrive` estimate predicts a future value of the `isAtFactory` attribute of the `Worker` component. We use the values of the attributes available at the time of prediction as inputs to the machine learning model—`dayOfWeek` in the example. Furthermore, we need to specify how far into the future we want to be able to predict—this is set by the `T+<min_t,max_t>` expression. This will influence what data we collect for training—we allow the time difference between inputs and outputs to be in the range $\langle min_t, max_t \rangle$.

To train the machine learning model, we need to collect training data. Our focus is on predictions of values, which can be observed at some point in the future. In the example, we predict whether the worker will come or not, and after some time, we can observe whether they really came or not. We thus need to observe these values and use them for the training of the model.

To collect the training data, we use the following procedure. In every time step of the simulation (every minute in the example), we check the guard, and if it marks the data as valid, we collect the values of input attributes and tag them with the current time. After that, we collect the values of the output attributes for the current time step and link them with past inputs. Specifically, we go through all the allowed time differences $t \in \langle min_t, max_t \rangle$ and save the training example $(t, inputs_at_now - t, outputs_now)$. The inputs

are collected throughout the whole run of the simulation, and the training is performed after the simulation finishes.

3.2.2 Time-to-condition estimate

The time-to-condition estimate predicts the time until a certain event occurs in the system. In the example in Section 3.1.2, the `timeToFailure` predicts how long a production machine will keep running before it is shut off due to a high failure rate of produced parts. The event, for which we predict the time, is the `failureRate` exceeding a threshold. The value of the attribute `failureRate` at the time of prediction is used as an input to the machine-learning model.

The training data for the machine learning model are collected as follows. In every time step of the simulation (every minute in the example), we check the guard, and if it marks the data as valid, we collect the values of input attributes and save them to a buffer together with the current time. Then, we check the target condition. If the condition is true, we take all the records in the buffer and associate them with the time difference between the current time and the time they were added to the buffer. The time difference is later used as a target (true output) for the training of the model. We clear the buffer.

4 Heuristics

The ML abstractions we introduced so far address the problem of classification and regression (i.e., tasks that can be addressed by supervised learning). The key prerequisite for supervised learning is the presence of samples along with ground truth. This is difficult to achieve for situations that are more combinatorial in nature.

Examples here are, for instance: (a) creating a maximum number of disjunctive groups of exactly $m \dots n$ components, (b) creating a maximum number of groups such that a component appears at least in m groups and at most in n groups, (c) the same but with a predicate that determines whether a component may be included in a group, (d) the same but with maximization a utility over the groups rather than maximizing their total number.

These abstract examples relate to situations when it is necessary to assign robots to collaborating groups based on their capabilities or attend to as many victims as possible.

In our example (in Section 2), this case arises in situations when late workers are canceled. At this point, it is necessary to select replacements from the standby workers. As this is not a prediction problem, we do not use machine learning (which we presented in the previous section). Rather we look for abstractions that allow us to specify component partitioning.

The problem here is that the assignment of standby worker is mutually exclusive – a standby worker cannot be assigned in place of two different late workers. This leads to an optimization problem, which has known inputs (i.e., components and their attributes, including the predicted ones) and known constraints.

An optimal selection of the standbys, considering for instance shared standbys among shifts, is an NP-complete problem. We faced this issue extensively in our previous work [5], where we were transforming ensembles to the constraint optimization problem. Even for small problem instances, the constraint optimization problem would soon become too computationally expensive to solve.

However, in this particular case, the optimal solution is not necessary (i.e., the correctness of the system here does not depend on whether the standbys are selected optimally but only that selections do not overlap—note that this is in strict contrast with the access permission assignment, where strict correctness is necessary). Fortunately, there are a number of heuristic algorithms that target such problems (i.e., NP-hard or complete problems). For example, a well-known and widely used heuristic algorithm is a k-means clustering method [6], which partitions n elements into k clusters in which each element belongs to the cluster with the nearest mean. By itself, the problem is NP-complete, but the k-means clustering method quickly converges to a local optimum.

In the case of the standbys selection, the exclusive choice method (e.g., [7]) can be used. Listing 6 shows the updated version of the `ReplaceLateWithStandbys` ensemble. Now, the selection of standbys is performed with the help of a special operation (line 5), where the exclusive choice heuristic method is implemented.

```

1 ensemble type CancelLateWorkers
2 # ... shortened here
3 inner ensemble type ReplaceLateWithStandbys
4     dynamic role standBys[lateWorkers.size]: Worker
5         exclusiveSelect worker from globalStandBys
6         action notify standBys with calledIn

```

Listing 6 Ensemble specification with heuristic operation

The above-mentioned k-means clustering method could be employed in our example, e.g., for clustering workers for optimized delivery of sensor data (i.e., workers are equipped with sensors, and to reduce the amount of communication, the measurements are not delivered directly, but they are aggregated by a worker that is "in-the-middle" of each cluster).

The downside of the use of heuristics is that they target individual problems. Therefore it is complicated to create a common "heuristics extension" for ML-DEECo, and particular heuristics need to be offered as specialized operations. However, our experience shows that there is only a limited number of problems in ensemble-based systems related to the assignment of components to ensembles: selection (exclusively select a fixed number of components for each ensemble instance), partitioning (split all components in a set among a set of known ensemble instances), clustering (split all components to an optimal unknown number of ensembles). For these, abstractions like the `exclusiveSelect` above can be created.

As a future work, we plan to create a detailed classification of problems related to ensemble-based systems and based on it, to design a set of common—at least to some extent—heuristics for ML-DEECo.

Specifically, we foresee the integration of clustering algorithms and optimization algorithms along the examples given in the introduction to this section. What we also see as having strong potential is the combination of supervised ML methods with the heuristics. This allows performing the clustering or optimization based on predicted values—e.g., to distribute components to geographical groups based on estimation when they are going to be in half an hour.

5 Evaluation

We center the evaluation around two arguments: (1) it saves on implementation effort to have machine learning abstractions part of the component model, (2) for certain situations the machine learning

allows the systems to perform better than just with rigid adaptation rules.

To this end, we have implemented a simulation of the running example using the ML-DEECo Python framework.

From the perspective of implementation effort, when using the abstractions of ML-DEECo realized by our Python implementation, the introduction of machine learning consist essentially only in declaring the predictor and providing annotations to component fields and ensemble roles. The exact code can be found in the replication package [2]. All this amounts to approx. 25 lines of code. On the other hand, custom implementation using TensorFlow or PyTorch frameworks would amount to at least a hundred lines of code (taking into account the data collection, pre-processing, training, retraining, and inference—all taken care of by ML-DEECo).

In addition to the Industry 4.0 example presented in this paper, we have used ML-DEECo to model also scenarios from smart farming. In all cases, the abstractions featured by ML-DEECo proved to be expressive enough to cover various supervised learning situations—including predictions of future states of sensors (i.e., continuous data), prediction of the future state of a component (i.e., discrete data), predictions about the existence of an ensemble, and predictions about which components will be members of an ensemble.

To illustrate that machine learning has the potential to outperform rigid adaptation rules, we simulated the Industry 4.0 example described in the paper.

In order to provide an easy-to-follow evaluation, we separate the example into two parts—a simulation of *Late workers* and *Production machines*.

5.1 Late workers

The configuration of the simulation is as follows. We assume that the workers arrive by a bus which stops a few minutes from the main gate of the factory. During business days, the bus arrives 24 minutes before the shift starts, and during weekends, the bus arrives 30 minutes before the shift. Furthermore, we assume that 10% of the workers are late each day and they arrive by a later bus—18 minutes before the start of the shift on business days and 15 minutes before the shift during weekends. To have more uncertainty in the environment,

we add a random delay (with exponential distribution) to each worker. If a worker is canceled and replaced by a standby, we assume that it will take 30 minutes before the standby arrives. We chose these values after careful deliberation to have something that both illustrate the system and are close to what the reality would look like.

We ran the simulation with three shifts starting at the same time, each with 100 workers, for three iterations. In the first iteration, we use the rigid rule of canceling workers 16 minutes before their shift starts. In the following two iterations, we use the machine-learning-based estimate described in Section 3 to decide whether to cancel the worker. The ML-based estimate is trained after each iteration (week)—first, we train it on the data collected while using the rigid rule (denoted “Training 1” in the figure below), then, we update it using data collected in the second week (“Training 2”).

The results are shown in Figure 4. The blue points are the number of necessary standbys (averaged over the shifts) with a blue line showing the average over the business days and weekends. The *lateness* (shown in orange) is computed as the square of the delay of workers who arrive late at their workplace. Since the goal of the system is to maximize the productivity of the smart factory, lower values of both the number of necessary standbys and the lateness indicate better performance of the system. It is clear that for this configuration, the learned rules perform significantly better than the rigid rule as the number of necessary standbys as well as the lateness are reduced when the ML-based estimate is employed.

We have further inspected the outputs of the machine learning model to see what the learned threshold for cancellation is. The outputs are shown in Figure 5. We observe that the learned threshold is different for business days and for weekends (as we want it to be). The model is more forgiving to the workers than the rigid rule—it allows them to enter the factory at latest 12 minutes before the shift starts on business days, and 7 minutes before the shift starts on weekends. It seems that it is beneficial to wait for the workers arriving by the later bus instead of calling the standbys which will take longer to arrive.

Furthermore, we have tried running the simulation with 20% and 30% of late workers to see the impact on the learning process. The results were

Fig. 4 Results of the simulation with 100 workers. Both the number of necessary standbys and the lateness of workers is reduced when ML-enabled rule is employed (after “Training 1”).

Fig. 5 Outputs of the neural network for predicting whether a worker will arrive to the factory before their shift starts (green) or not (red).

very similar and the learned rule performed significantly better than the rigid one. For 30% of late workers, the difference in the cancellation time for business days and for weekends was not that big, but it is still clear that the network was capable of learning the pattern. The plots with results for 20% and 30% of late workers are available in the replication package [2].

In the example, we focused on a single source of uncertainty—the arrival of the workers. Other type of uncertainty in the example could be predicting whether a worker actually grabs the headgear. This is essentially an identical problem to the uncertainty of the workers arrival, only the predicted values are not continuous but discrete (and thus the underlying neural network would differ only in the last layer that would use softmax, and in

the loss function that would use categorical cross-entropy). For the sake of conciseness, we focused on a single example only.

5.2 Production machines

We also implemented a simulation of the *Production machine* example mentioned in Section 3.1.2. We have a production machine, which has a failure rate that grows in time (in every time step, the failure rate increases by 0.05 with 10% probability). When the failure rate reaches 0.5, the machine is shut off and a maintenance team is called to repair the machine. In our simulation, the machine runs in expectation for 100 time steps before it fails (it needs to be shut off). The maintenance team arrives and repairs the machine 30 time steps after it is called.

We employ the estimate to predict how long the machine will keep running before it fails and a maintenance is necessary. If we predict that the machine will survive for only 30 time steps or less, we call the maintenance team in advance, so it hopefully arrives before the failure rate of the machine is too high and it needs to be shut off.

We ran a simulation with 100 machines for 1000 time steps. In the reactive scenario (call maintenance when machine fails), the machines were active 78.3% of the time. With the ML-based proactive adaptation, the machines were running 93.9% of the time. We also tried a simpler rigid proactive solution – call the maintenance team 70 time steps after the last repair, which resulted in machines

running for 89.9% of the time. The results are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 Summary of the simulation results for `ProductionMachine` component.

Scenario	Machines active time
Reactive	78.3%
Proactive (Rigid)	89.9%
Proactive (ML)	93.9%

In Figures 6, 7, and 8 we show the failure rate and running state of one of the machines in the simulation for the reactive, rigid proactive, and ML-based proactive scenarios respectively. When the failure rate reaches 0.5, the machine is shut off, which can be seen in the bottom part of the charts where red color indicates that the machine is not running.

Obviously, the rigid proactive solution is very sensitive to the threshold for calling the maintenance team (70 time steps after the last repair in our case). By setting the threshold, the number of calls to the maintenance team and the need to shut off the machines can be balanced. A benefit of the ML-based approach is that the threshold is set automatically by the learning algorithm.

We have also tested several other variants of the failure rate schedule (the rate at which the failure rate is increased in a production machine).

With a sigmoidal schedule (the failure rate is computed as a random variable with mean computed as $\frac{1}{2}\sigma(0.1 \cdot (\text{timeSinceLastRepair} - 70))$), the results were very similar: In the reactive scenario, the machines were active 76.1% of the time. In the rigid proactive scenario, the machines were active 93.6% of the time. And in the ML-based proactive adaptation, the machines were running 97.0% of the time.

With an exponential failure rate schedule (failure rate increasing exponentially in the time since last repair), the proactive scenarios were again more successful in preventing the machine shut-off than the reactive scenario. However, as the growth of the failure rate was faster in this case, the differences between the rigid proactive and the ML-based proactive scenarios were smaller.

5.3 Limitations

The evaluation we presented serves as an indication of an illustration of the potential of our approach. Due to the limited size of the use case, we refrain from claiming the generality of the approach. However, at least our indicative experiments show its potential.

We aimed to give generality to the abstractions by constructing them independently of a particular use case. We based the abstractions on a taxonomy prediction (briefly discussed in Section 3)—i.e., associating predictions with a component, ensemble, or component-ensemble pair and classifying types of predictions. This is independent of our use case and has been built as a combination of generally accepted abstractions.

In our evaluations, the ML-based approach shows an improvement over adaptation based on rigid rules. However, when comparing the ML-based proactive scenario with the rigid proactive scenario in the Production machines example (5.2), the improvement is smaller. Furthermore, by carefully tuning the threshold in the rigid proactive scenario (after how long since the last repair to call the maintenance team), the rigid proactive scenario can surpass the ML-based proactive scenario (however, at the cost of calling the repair team more often).

Other limitations of applying ML for self-adaptation, that we do not discuss in detail in this paper, include scalability, performance considerations (ML is usually slower than rigid adaptation rules), and the need for proper ML algorithm and parameter selection. [8]

Our work is limited to supervised learning only. We are currently in the process of extending ML-DEECO of reinforcement learning.

6 Related Work

In the paper, we have presented a component model targeting the development of adaptive systems and employing machine learning techniques directly at the level of a system architecture specification. Thus, the related areas are approaches defining explicit component models for adaptive systems and approaches combining adaptive systems with machine learning techniques—ideally, approaches combining both.

Fig. 6 Failure rate and running state of one production machine in the reactive scenario. Compared to Figures 7 and 8, the machine spends more time shut off (indicated by the red portions spanning more time of the “Machine not running” part of the chart).

Fig. 7 Failure rate and running state of one production machine in a rigid proactive scenario. The machine spends less time shut off than in the Reactive scenario (Figure 6). However, the maintenance team is called more often (when the maintenance arrives, the failure rate drops from 0.5 to 0) – 10 times instead of 7 times in the Reactive scenario.

Fig. 8 Failure rate and running state of one production machine in the ML-based proactive scenario. The fraction of time when the machine is shut off is the smallest among all the scenarios.

Using machine-learning techniques in adaptive systems is not a new approach. In [9], a systematic literature review (SLR) analyzes the employment of machine learning techniques in adaptive systems for the past 20 years. From the analysis, an apparent increasing trend in their usage can be seen, and the machine learning techniques are mainly employed in the adaptation phase. Also from the same area is the SLR in [8] which also confirms the increasing usage of machine learning techniques in adaptive systems—again mainly in the adaptation phase to optimize it and/or predict future actions. Nevertheless, most of the analyzed approaches use machine learning techniques “under-the-hood” in their implementation. This is in strict contrast with our approach, where we explicitly use and expose them for the architecture specification. In the text below, we discuss selected related approaches in more detail.

There are different uses for machine learning in self-adaptive systems ranging from predicting sensor values to reducing the space of adaptations. E.g., in [10] neural networks are employed for such a reduction. A similar approach [11] (by a similar group of authors) combines machine-learning techniques with a cost-based analysis to reduce the space and choose an adaptation with the best cost. In [12], a theorem defining a theoretical bound on the impact of applying a machine-learning method during adaptation was defined, and an approach for reducing an adaptation space was proposed. The paper [13] proposes a framework for the coevolution of an adaptive system together with its tests. Machine-learning is used for restrictions of an adaptation space in order to achieve a meaningful system as a result of an adaption step. An approach of a combination of machine-learning techniques and probabilistic model checking is described in the paper [14] and used for choosing the best adaptation and refusing unfeasible ones. The approach thus allows for fast convergence towards optimal decisions. Online reinforcement learning is used in [15] to deal with design-time uncertainty and automation of the development of the self-adaptation logic. Thanks to automation, there is thus no need for manual activities during the application of reinforcement learning. In the SARDE framework [16], machine learning is used for the selection of the best estimation approach and for optimization of the selected approaches. The whole framework then allows for self-adaptive resource

demand estimation. In [17], machine-learning is utilized for forecasting values of QoS parameters and, therefore, for advanced and proactive selection of possible adaptation strategies.

As mentioned, the approaches in the paragraph above use machine-learning techniques internally for a particular functionality of a system/framework. This is in contrast with our approach, where we are targeting the creation of architectural abstractions allowing for the usage of machine learning during the design of a self-adaptive system and direct use of machine-learning results at the architectural level.

This leads to the second area of related works—component models for adaptive systems and especially those that offer implementation in a common programming language. The Service Component Ensemble Language (SCEL) [18] laid the mathematical foundations and semantics for ensemble-based systems. Later, the concepts of SCEL were implemented in a Java-based runtime framework called jRESP [19]. Another implementation of the ensemble-based concepts can be found in Helena, which is a complete framework for developing ensemble-based systems [20]. An approach similar to ensembles can be found in the *AbC* calculus [21] that defines systems via attribute-based communication between components. The calculus has been formalized in [22]. Implementation of *AbC* is available as the *Ab^aCuS* framework [23]. Similar to our implementation of ML-DEECo, components in *Ab^aCuS* are modeled as classes, and processes (performing communication via component attributes similarly to ensembles) are also classes. Another implementation of *AbC* is ABEL [24] that is a DSL developed in the Erlang language. Dynamic logic for describing ensemble-based communication between components is defined in [25], and it is implemented in a variant of the *AbC* calculus. The DReAM framework [26] allows for specifications of dynamically reconfigurable architectures. Its architecture description language is based on an interaction logic and describes dynamic coordination among components. Static parts of the architecture are described using a propositional interaction logic, while DReAM describes dynamic coordination. The Java implementation of DReAM, similarly to our approach, maps components and coordination to classes. The BIP component model [27] is used as a basis for the propositional interaction logic

employed in DReAM. BIP primarily focuses on the formal description of component behavior. A combination of UML components and BIP is proposed in [28], and it focuses on the description and verification of component behavior and inter-component communication. An extension of BIP is DR-BIP [29] that adds support for dynamic reconfigurations.

The approaches for modeling and implementing ensemble-based (and similar) architecture primarily focus on semantics but they do not introduce any machine-learning on the architectural (or even any other) level. This contrasts with our approach, where we enrich the ensemble-based systems with machine-learning techniques.

Table 2 further summarizes all of the discussed related work. The ++ means that the feature is fully supported, + stands for a partial support, while an empty space means no support at all.

	Architecture abstractions	Logic-based adaptation rules	ML-based adaptation
[10]			++
[11]			++
[12]			++
[13]		+	++
[14]			++
[15]			++
[16]			++
[17]			++
[18]	+	++	
[19]	+	++	
[20]	++	++	
[21]		++	
[22]	+	++	
[23]	+	++	
[24]	+	++	
[25]	++	++	
[26]	++	++	
[27]	+	++	
[28]	++	++	
[29]	+	++	
ML-DEECo	++	++	++

Table 2 Related work summary

7 Conclusion

In this paper, we have presented ML-DEECo, a novel ensemble-based component model that features abstractions for machine learning (namely

the supervised learning) and heuristics related to the assignment of tasks to components (realized by component membership in an ensemble). We have presented three kinds of estimates based on where they can be applied in an architecture (on a component, an ensemble, and a component-ensemble pair) and two kinds of estimates based on what they predict (value, and time-to-condition). We illustrated the key abstractions and evaluated the approach on two examples from our past project in Industry 4.0 domain.

In the future, we aim at featuring abstractions related to unsupervised and reinforcement learning, as they would cover situations when the ground trues cannot be observed at all (note that in this paper we assume that the ground trues cannot be observed at the time the prediction is performed but will be observable at a later point of time). Another direction for future work is to design a set of common heuristics for ML-DEECo.

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